

INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES (ICT) AS A TOOL FOR THE IMPROVEMENT OF ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

In order to develop this article, a documentary review of the elaboration and production of research works related to the study of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and the Improvement of Environmental Management was carried out through a bibliometric study to know the main characteristics of 59 publications registered in the Scopus database. The results obtained from this database were organized in graphs and figures, categorizing the information by variables such as Year of Publication, Country of Origin and Area of Knowledge, which allowed to identify, through qualitative analysis, the position of different authors regarding the proposed topic. The main findings of this research were that Brazil stood out for having the highest scientific production, leading the list with 19 publications. Likewise, the area of knowledge that made the greatest contribution to the construction of bibliographic material related to the study of variables was environmental science, with 19 published documents.

Keywords: Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), Environmental Management Improvement.

1. Introduction

Much is said about Information and Communication Technologies, also known by their acronym ICT, due to the continuous struggle of states and governments to expand their coverage and thus be able to reach any rural or urban area of a country. However, little seems to be known about the positive impact that ICTs have on the different aspects of our daily lives. The term ICT encompasses traditional and modern tools that have been used to communicate, such as radio and television, social networks, applications or web platforms that allow people to interact and access information of interest to them. Although this definition is usually approached from a different focus than the environmental one, it is important to highlight that this type of technologies “are a fundamental tool for monitoring, mitigating and adapting to climate change, as well as to face energy challenges and play an important role in the management of natural disasters and emergencies” (United Nations, 2013). Hence the relationship between ICTs and Environmental Management is a process that seeks to prevent and, in cases that require it, provide solutions to problems involving nature and a given

society. The joint work between both variables could generate the reduction of gases resulting from the greenhouse effect, as well as efficient use of resources, and transformation of production mechanisms, all this under the promotion of a greater awareness of consumption among people and companies contributing to other determining factors such as the economy, social justice, among others. For this reason, this article seeks to describe the main characteristics of the set of publications attached to the Scopus database that is directly related to the variables mentioned above, as well as the description of the position of certain authors affiliated with institutions around the world, during the period between 2017 and 2021 at the Latin American level.

2. General Objective

To analyze from a bibliometric and bibliographic perspective, the elaboration of research papers on the variables Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and the Improvement of Environmental Management in Scopus.

3. Methodology

This article is conducted through a mixed research approach combining quantitative and qualitative methods.

On the one hand, a quantitative analysis of the information selected in Scopus is carried out under a bibliometric approach of scientific production corresponding to the study of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) as a tool for the Improvement of Environmental Management.

On the other hand, from a qualitative perspective, examples of some research works published in the area of the study mentioned above are analyzed from a bibliographic approach that allows describing the position of different authors on the proposed topic.

It is important to note that the entire search was carried out through Scopus, establishing the parameters referenced in *Figure 1*.

3.1 Methodological design

Figure 1. Methodological design
Source: Own elaboration

3.1.1 Phase 1: Data Collection

The data collection was executed from the Search tool on the Scopus web page, where 36 publications were obtained from the choice of the following filters:

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TITLE-ABS-KEY (information AND communication AND technologies, AND environmental AND management) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2021) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2020) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017) AND (LIMIT-TO (AFFILCOUNTRY (AFFILCOUNTRY ,“Brazil”) OR LIMIT-TO (AFFILCOUNTRY , “Mexico”) OR LIMIT-TO (AFFILCOUNTRY ,“Colombia”) OR LIMIT-TO (AFFILCOUNTRY , “Peru”) OR LIMIT-TO (AFFILCOUNTRY , “Argentina”) OR LIMIT-TO (AFFILCOUNTRY , “Ecuador”) OR LIMIT-TO (AFFILCOUNTRY ,“Chile”) OR LIMIT-TO (AFFILCOUNTRY , “Uruguay”) OR LIMIT-TO (AFFILCOUNTRY ,“Cuba”) OR LIMIT-TO (AFFILCOUNTRY ,“Panama”))

- ❖ Published documents whose study variables are related to Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and the Improvement of Environmental Management.
- ❖ Limited to the years 2017-2021.
- ❖ Limited to Latin American countries.
- ❖ Without distinction of area of knowledge.
- ❖ Without distinction of type of publication.

3.1.2 Phase 2: Construction of analysis material

The information collected in Scopus during the previous phase is organized and subsequently classified through graphs, figures and tables as follows:

- ❖ Word Co-occurrence.
- ❖ Year of publication
- ❖ Country of origin of the publication.
- ❖ Knowledge area.
- ❖ Type of Publication

3.1.3 Phase 3: Drafting conclusions and final document

In this phase, the study analyzed the results previously obtained, resulting in the determination of conclusions and, consequently, the final document.

4. Results

4.1 Co-occurrence of words

Figure 2 shows the Co-occurrence of keywords found in the publications identified in the Scopus database.

Figure 2. Cooccurrence of words

Source: Own elaboration (2022); based on data exported from Scopus.

As mentioned above, the data in Figure 2 were exported from Scopus, showing the variables and their relationship with other terms such as substantivity, sustainable development, risk management, disaster prevention, and procedures, among others are analyzed below.

For good environmental management, it is essential to carry out studies and research to determine how resources can be used without causing serious environmental damage and preserve them for future generations to work together in the sustainable and sustainable development of these resources. It is for this reason that humans from state or non-state organizations have sought ways to use Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) to obtain relevant information that allows them to make assertive decisions in the processes that make up environmental management, such as prevention and disaster management, recycling and any information related to the conservation and protection of the environment.

4.2 Distribution of scientific production by year of publication

Figure 3 shows the distribution of scientific production according to the year of publication.

Figure 3. Distribution of scientific production by year of publication.
Source: Own elaboration (2022); based on data exported from Scopus.

Figure 3 shows the scientific production concerning the variables Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and the Improvement of Environmental Management, at the Latin American level, between the years 2017 and 2021, left as a result of the publication of 59 documents containing the keywords. Likewise, throughout the period, several changes were experienced. It starts with 2017, where the lowest number of documents published during the period is observed, a figure that increases the following year considerably with a total of 13 publications. Although in 2019, the figure decreased, it did not remain the same or below the initial figure, increasing gradually during the following two years, achieving the preparation and subsequent publication of 12 and 17 documents, respectively, on the platform.

The latter highlight the conference proceedings “Design and implementation of a flexible platform for remote monitoring of environmental variables” (Izaguirre et al., 2021) in which, as suggested by its title, a system based on “flexible architecture, energy autonomy and remote communication” is designed and implemented to facilitate data collection and remote monitoring of environmental variables, proving its effectiveness in “monitoring the sound of beehives for the control of environmental pollution and determining the amount of phosphorus and nitrogen present in the water of river courses” (de Izaguirre et al., 2021).

4.3 Distribution of scientific production by country of origin.

Figure 4 shows the distribution of scientific production according to the nationality of the authors.

Figure 4. Distribution of scientific production by country of origin.
Source: Own elaboration (2022); based on data provided by Scopus.

In the study of the Relationship between Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and the Improvement of Environmental Management, Brazil leads the list of published papers with a total of 19 records in the Scopus database during the period of the years 2017-2021, followed by Mexico and Colombia, with 11 and 8 texts, respectively.

From Colombia is the article entitled “Evaluation of sports tourism in the city of Cartagena-Colombia from environmental management and information and communication technologies” (Alvarado et al., 2020), which shows the concern of tourism service providers to transform their locations into spaces “that comply with sustainability and social responsibility criteria and their environmental performance is eco-friendly” (Alvarado et al., 2020). Therefore, it was determined necessary to rely on Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) to recognize the best options for their economy and territory and attract a greater number of tourists through the socialization of their projects for environmental purposes.

At this point, it is important to note that the elaboration of scientific publications, in many cases, is based on collaborations that may involve private and public institutions from one or several countries. Therefore, the same publication may be linked to one or more authors with different nationalities and thus to more than one country simultaneously, making part of each of the total number of articles or publications in the final sum. *Figure 5* below shows in greater detail the flow of collaborative work carried out by several countries.

Figure 5. Co-citations between countries.

Source: Own elaboration (2022); based on data provided by Scopus.

Figure 5 shows the research grouping according to the collaboration between authors from different international institutions. There is outstanding participation between authors affiliated with institutions in Latin American countries such as Colombia, Brazil, Mexico, and Peru and foreign countries such as the United States and Spain.

4.4 Distribution of scientific production by area of knowledge

Figure 6 shows the distribution of the production of scientific publications according to the area of knowledge through which the different research methodologies are implemented.

Figure 6. Distribution of scientific production by area of knowledge.
Source: Own elaboration (2022); based on data provided by Scopus.

Due to the importance of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in the Improvement of Environmental Management, it is not surprising that most of the publications in the Scopus database on our variables are made from the area of environmental science, occupying the main position in the publication of documents. Other areas, such as engineering, computer science, and social sciences, have contributed to the study of these variables, publishing 16, 14 and 12 documents, respectively.

As seen in *Figure 6*, the variables that are the subject of this study are relevant in various areas of knowledge since they directly influence the decisions made regarding the protection, preservation and use of the natural resources of the environmental system of a territory or country.

4.5 Type of publication

Figure 7 shows the distribution of the bibliographic findings according to the type of publication made by each of the authors found in Scopus.

Figure 7. Type of publication

Source: Own elaboration (2022); based on data provided by Scopus.

Figure 7 clearly shows that the predominant type of publication in the study of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in the Improvement of Environmental Management was the journal article with a total of 35 documents. In second place were conference proceedings with 15, followed by reviews with only 5 publications.

One of the best advantages of using Information and Communication Technologies as a tool in the Improvement of Environmental Management is the ability to prevent risks and disasters by detecting early warnings that can safeguard the lives of entire populations, which is the topic of the article entitled “Information and Communication Technologies in the management of social and environmental disaster risk” (Mattedi & Ludwig, 2018), which analyzes the relationship between both variables and identifies three characteristics in “information and communication flow in disaster risk management - DRM” (Mattedi & Ludwig, 2018).

5. Conclusions

Finally, thanks to the bibliometric analysis carried out in this research work, it was possible to establish that Brazil was the country with the largest number of published records regarding the variables Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and Improvement of Environmental Management with a total of 19 publications in Scopus database during the period 2017-2021 in Latin America. Likewise, it was determined that journal articles led the type of publication thanks to the elaboration of 35 texts and that environmental science was the area with the highest number of studies concerning the subject matter in the years and countries mentioned above.

First of all, using ICTs as a tool for improving environmental management has allowed positive changes in each of the projects, facilitating access to relevant data such as water pollution levels and environmental pollution control. Likewise, access to environmental information through ICTs allows identifying similarities between societies and territories based on their characteristics and

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environmental problems, which allows the replication of previously successful models of sustainability and sustainability.

On the other hand, at the business level, the use of ICTs has led to certain processes being carried out virtually or digitally, thus reducing the emissions generated by the excessive printing of documents and damages resulting from the actions executed on a daily basis. Despite this, Latin American countries still face great challenges that make it difficult to obtain all the benefits that could result from using ICTs to improve environmental management. One of the most relevant is the lack of coverage that continues to be the main issue in some regions, where despite the efforts made, major changes have not been achieved in the use of resources and, therefore, in the reduction of social inequality.

Because of the above, it can be concluded that greater investment is needed in Latin American countries to achieve total coverage and access of their populations to Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs), which will directly improve the quality of life of individuals as a result of better use of resources and, consequently, a preserved environment. Only when this need is met will it be possible to improve environmental management.

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